

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TESTOSTERONE, FSH, AND LH IN DIABETIC AND NON-DIABETIC INDIVIDUALS: A CASE-CONTROL STUDY

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Abstract

Objectives:

Diabetes is a metabolic disorder that affects various body organs and hormones, especially sex hormones. Different studies have found the association of sex hormones with diabetes differently. This study aims to accurately compare serum total testosterone, FSH, and LH levels in diabetic and non-diabetic individuals, as well as the relationship between testosterone and with age of patients and the duration of diabetes.

Methods:

This case-control study was conducted from June to October 2023 at Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar, Pakistan, involving 101 diabetic males and 101 non-diabetic individuals. Blood was collected in a gel tube, centrifuged, and HbA1c, Serum total testosterone, FSH, and LH were tested by cobass411 through the Electrochemiluminescence immunoassay (ECLIA) method.

Results:

Serum total testosterone was significantly lower in type 2 diabetic patients (2.41 ± 1.76) than in non-diabetic individuals (4.49 ± 1.34) (p value=0.000). LH was significantly higher in diabetic (7.93 ± 6.25) than non-diabetic individuals (5.13 ± 2.02) (p value=0.000), with no effect on FSH in both groups. The duration of diabetes and testosterone had no significant relationship. In contrast, a significantly negative relationship was seen in both age groups: Group 1 =35-45 (mean rank=108.04) and Group 2 = 46-75 (mean rank=90.99), and testosterone level (p value=0.041).

Conclusion:

In diabetic patients, diabetes affects testosterone and LH as compared to non-diabetic individuals, whereas FSH remains normal in both groups. Testosterone decreases as age increases in diabetic patients, but the duration of diabetes has no impact on testosterone levels.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a chronic disorder in which blood glucose levels rise because glucose cannot be metabolized in cells due to insufficient insulin production by the pancreas [1]. In 2017, 415 million people were living with diabetes, of which

90% had type 2 diabetes, and an estimated 190 million individuals had undiagnosed diabetes [2]. According to the National Diabetic Survey of Pakistan conducted in 2016-17, approximately 27.4 million cases (26.3%) of diabetes were

reported among individuals aged 20 years and above [3][4].

There are two primary types of diabetes: Type 1 and Type 2. Type 1 diabetes is characterized by the autoimmune destruction of beta cells in the pancreas, leading to the complete absence of insulin secretion [5]. Type 2 diabetes, on the other hand, is a chronic disorder that arises when the body's cells develop an inadequate insulin response. Insulin is a hormone responsible for regulating blood glucose levels by facilitating the transfer of glucose from the bloodstream into cells to meet energy requirements. In Type 2 diabetes, cells become resistant to insulin, resulting in elevated blood glucose levels and leading to a condition known as hyperglycemia [6].

Type 2 diabetes is more prevalent than Type 1 diabetes, with etiological factors such as age, obesity, physical inactivity, poor nutrition, and family history contributing to its development [7]. Uncontrolled diabetes can lead to severe complications, including damage to organs, heart attack, stroke, kidney failure, and vision problems, primarily due to its detrimental effects on nerves and blood vessels [1].

Type 2 diabetes mellitus significantly impacts body hormones, particularly sex hormones such as testosterone, follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), and luteinizing hormone (LH), which can adversely affect reproductive ability and overall physical capabilities, especially in younger individuals [8]. The anterior lobe of the pituitary gland secretes FSH and LH. In males, FSH plays a crucial role in spermatogenesis, while LH stimulates the secretion of testosterone [9]. Low serum testosterone is mainly reported in diabetic patients [1][10]. A study illustrated that plasma testosterone levels, follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), and luteinizing hormone (LH) were significantly lower in diabetic patients [11]. Another study has also reported that serum-free testosterone was significantly low in diabetic patients as compared to non-diabetic, while there was no significant difference seen between serum FSH and LH in diabetic and non-diabetic men [12].

The study also showed a significant decrease in FSH and LH levels in diabetic patients as compared to control [13].

A study found that the decline in testosterone levels was not associated with the duration of diabetes but was associated with obesity, high C-reactive protein, and mild anemia [14].

Previous Studies have shown different associations between FSH and LH in diabetic patients. Therefore, this study aimed to accurately compare serum total testosterone, FSH, and LH in diabetic and non-diabetic individuals and to identify the association of serum total testosterone with the duration of diabetes and the age of the individuals.

Materials and Methods:

This case-control study was conducted at Lady Reading Hospital (LRH) in Peshawar, Pakistan, from June to December 2024. The study received approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of LRH and Khyber Medical University. A total of 202 participants were included in the study, with sample size calculated using OpenEpi. The cohort comprised 101 diabetic male patients and 101 healthy controls. Diabetic patients with HbA1c levels greater than 6.5% were included, while individuals with conditions such as hypogonadism, panhypopituitarism, coronary heart disease, those using hormone-influencing medications, and those with a history of HIV or renal failure were excluded.

Five milliliters of blood were collected from each participant, centrifuged at high speed, and the serum was analyzed for luteinizing hormone (LH), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), and testosterone levels using the Cobas e 411 analyzer (Roche Diagnostics).

Data was analyzed using SPSS version 26.0. Descriptive statistics were presented in tabulated form. To determine the level of significance Mann-Whitney U test was applied, and the results were presented in tabulated form. To assess the relationship between variables, Spearman's correlation was used, and the findings were illustrated in graphical form.

Results:

The study revealed that serum total testosterone levels in diabetic patients (2.41 ± 1.76) were significantly lower compared to non-diabetic individuals (4.49 ± 1.34) ($p = 0.00$). In contrast, luteinizing hormone (LH) concentrations in diabetic patients (7.93 ± 6.25) were significantly higher than in nondiabetic individuals (5.13 ± 2.02) ($p = 0.00$), while follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) levels showed no significant difference between the two groups (Table 1).

follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), and luteinizing hormone (LH) in people with diabetes and without diabetes.

Table 1: A comparison of the mean blood concentration of total testosterone (TT),

	Diabetic			Non-Diabetic			P value
	Mean	SD	Mean Rank	Mean	SD	Mean Rank	
Testosterone (ng/ml)	2.41	1.76	68.28	4.49	1.34	134.72	0.000
FSH (mIU/ml)	7.79	8.41	98.23	6.49	2.66	104.77	0.426
LH (mIU/ml)	7.93	6.25	118.25	5.13	2.02	84.75	0.000

Table 2: shows the effect of the duration of diabetes and age on Testosterone concentration

	Duration	No. of Patients	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	P Value
Testosterone	<6	42	42.94	1165.000	0.610
	>6	59	52.25		
	Age Group	No. of Patients	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	P Value
Testosterone	35-45	118	108.04	4066.000	0.041
	45-75	84	90.99		

Figure 1: Scatter plots of HbA1C with Testosterone, FSH, and LH

The results also demonstrated a significant negative correlation between serum total testosterone and HbA1c levels ($y = 5.74 - 0.29x$) and a slightly positive correlation between LH and HbA1c levels ($y = 4.18 + 0.3x$). However, no correlation was observed between FSH and HbA1c levels ($y = 6.93 + 0.03x$) (Figure 1).

Furthermore, no significant relationship was found between HbA1c and testosterone levels in early diagnosed patients (duration <6 years; mean rank = 42.94) compared to late-diagnosed individuals (duration >6 years; mean rank = 52.25) ($p = 0.61$). Additionally, when participants were divided into two age groups (Group 1: 35–45 years and Group 2: 45–75 years), a significantly lower testosterone level was observed in Group 2 (mean rank = 90.99) compared to Group 1 (mean rank = 108.04) (Mann-Whitney $U = 4066.00$, $p = 0.04$) (Table 2).

Discussion:

The findings of this study determined that serum total testosterone levels were significantly lower in diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic individuals, while luteinizing hormone (LH) levels were significantly higher. However, follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) concentrations remained similar in both groups. These results are consistent with a previous study conducted in 2012, which also reported significantly lower total testosterone levels in diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic individuals, with no significant differences in FSH and LH concentrations between the two groups [10]. In contrast, another study from Iraq found that diabetic patients had significantly lower testosterone levels and significantly higher FSH and LH levels compared to non-diabetic individuals. This discrepancy may be attributed to the smaller sample size in the Iraqi study [15].

The observed decrease in testosterone levels and elevation in LH concentrations in diabetic patients may be influenced by several factors. One possible explanation is the reduced number or poor quality of Leydig cells in diabetic patients, which may lead to increased LH secretion to normalize circulating testosterone levels. Alternatively, it may be due to increased resistance of Leydig cells and follicular cells to gonadotropin-releasing hormones in diabetic patients, resulting in elevated LH secretion despite low or normal testosterone levels. These findings highlight the complex interplay between diabetes and hormonal regulation, particularly in the context of reproductive hormones [15].

Diabetes is a serious metabolic disorder that can lead to significant reproductive abnormalities, particularly in male patients. Nearly half of diabetic individuals experience poor quality and reduced amounts of sperm secretion. Several mechanisms have been identified to explain how diabetes impairs bodily functions. For instance, hyperglycemia induces oxidative stress, diabetic neuropathy, and insulin resistance, all of which can disrupt the function of the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, and gonads. These disruptions further affect the secretion of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), luteinizing hormone (LH), and testosterone. Additionally, glucose metabolism plays a critical role in spermatogenesis and sperm maturation. Diabetes can also damage blood vessels, reducing blood flow to reproductive organs, which may result in structural abnormalities in the testicles, stromal cells, and seminiferous tubules [16].

These findings underscore the profound impact of diabetes on reproductive health. However, despite the significant consequences, there is currently no specific treatment that focuses on addressing the reproductive health challenges faced by diabetic patients. This highlights the need for further research and development of targeted therapies to mitigate the reproductive complications associated with diabetes. This study shows that early diagnosis (Duration <6) and late diagnosis (Duration >6) have no impact on testosterone levels. These findings are supported by a previous study from Iraq, which classified the duration of the disease into three groups Group 1 = <5 , Group 2 = $>5 - 10$, and Group 3 = >10 Which determined that there is no significant difference between the duration of disease groups and testosterone levels [15].

This study also observed that testosterone levels decline with increasing age, a finding consistent with previous research. Earlier studies have reported that serum testosterone levels are lower in older individuals compared to younger ones, which aligns with the results of this study. This decline is attributed to a reduced testicular response to gonadotropins and hypothalamic activity in aging men [17][18].

In younger individuals, Leydig cells facilitate testosterone biosynthesis in response to luteinizing hormone (LH) secreted by the pituitary gland. However, in primary hypogonadism, which is more common in older age, the responsiveness of Leydig cells to LH diminishes. As a result, the pituitary gland increases LH secretion in an attempt to

stimulate testosterone production. Despite this elevated LH secretion, the hormone is unable to effectively bind to LH receptors on Leydig cells, leading to impaired testosterone biosynthesis. This age-related decline in testosterone production highlights the complex interplay between aging, hormonal regulation, and reproductive health [19][20].

Conclusion:

The findings of this study indicate that serum total testosterone levels are significantly lower, and luteinizing hormone (LH) levels are significantly higher in diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic individuals, while follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) levels remain unaffected. Additionally, the duration of diabetes does not appear to influence testosterone levels. However, a negative correlation was observed between the age of the patients and testosterone levels, suggesting that testosterone levels decline with advancing age. These results highlight the distinct hormonal imbalances associated with diabetes and underscore the impact of aging on testosterone production, independent of diabetes duration.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of this study, the following future recommendations can be proposed to explore further and address the implications of diabetes on reproductive health and hormonal imbalances:

Conduct studies with larger sample size and diverse populations to validate the findings and ensure broader applicability.

Investigate the underlying mechanisms by which diabetes affects the Leydig cell function, LH receptor sensitivity, and testosterone biosynthesis. This could include exploring oxidative stress, insulin resistance, and vascular damage in greater detail.

Study the effects of improved glycemic control on testosterone, LH, and FSH levels to determine whether better diabetes management can mitigate hormonal imbalances and improve reproductive outcomes.

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